

Supplementary Information

A new 3-Dimensional model to describe the complete human corneal oxygenation during contact lens wear

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Figures S1, S2, S3, S4, S5, S6, S7

Figure S1. Oxygen tension profiles in the axis and periphery of the eye for the three reference materials and optical powers -6 and $+6$ diopter under open-eye and closed-eye conditions.

Figure S2. Oxygen flux profiles in the axis and periphery of the eye for the three reference materials and optical powers -6 and $+6$ diopter under open-eye and closed-eye conditions.

Figure S3. Oxygen flux exchanged between eye layers as a function of the angle taken from the eye axis for the three reference materials and optical powers -6 and $+6$ diopter under open-eye and closed-eye conditions.

Figure S4. Oxygen consumption profiles ($\text{cm}^3(\text{O}_2) \cdot \text{cm}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$) using a Balafilcon A lens of -3 diopters under open-eye (up) and closed-eye (down) conditions.

Figure S5. Oxygen consumption profiles ($\text{cm}^3(\text{O}_2) \cdot \text{cm}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$) using a Balafilcon A lens of +3 diopters under open-eye conditions (up) and closed-eye (down) conditions.

Figure S6. Oxygen consumption profiles ($\text{cm}^3(\text{O}_2) \cdot \text{cm}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$) using a Lotrafilcon A lens of -3 diopters under open-eye conditions (up) and closed-eye (down) conditions.

Figure S7. Oxygen consumption profiles ($\text{cm}^3(\text{O}_2) \cdot \text{cm}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$) using a Lotrafalcon A lens of +3 diopters under open-eye conditions (up) and closed-eye (down) conditions.